

Sustainable agriculture practices using traditional climate predictions: A Study among pastoral and agro-pastoral communities in Degehabur Woreda, Somali regional Dtate, Ethiopia, East Africa

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Abstract

Nearly 9.8 million people (12% of total population of the country) of which 56 % are pastorals, 32% are agro-pastoral EEA, (2005) and Mulat,(1998). Based on the 2007 Census conducted by the Central Statistical Agency of Ethiopia (CSA), this Woreda has a total population of 115,555, 39.65% are pastoralists. Agriculture and related activities are important in securing livelihood for the pastoralists and agro- pastoralists in the African continents in general and Ethiopia in particular. Considering the regional distribution, Somali region takes the lion share (53%) Sandford and Habtu,(2000) where the land are rain- fed, therefore, climate-sensitive agricultural production system Tadesse, (2000) is more prone here. Today in modernization and post modernization era when science and technology play a pivotal role in the measuring of natural disabilities and climatic vagaries for human development. Pastorals and agro-pastorals in many parts of the Ethiopia still have their own believes and do practices on climate change to secure their sustainable livelihoods.

Key Words: Agriculture, Pastoral, Agro pastoralists, Climate, Traditional, Practices

Introduction

Background of the Study

Africa contains one-half of the world's pastoral peoples; thirteen million Africans are predominately pastoral and another nine million are agro-pastoral, keeping large numbers of livestock while practicing agriculture (Galaty & Johnson (1990); Jahnke, 1982).

Pastoral areas in Ethiopia, which cover about 0.7 million square km are generally known as the range lands. These areas support about 9.8 million people (12% of total population of the country) of which 56 % are pastorals, 32% are agro-pastoral and the remaining 22% are urban dwellers (EEA, 2005 and Mulat, 1998). Pastoralism relies on livestock diversity to exploit and make use of the diverse rangeland resources, and typical pastoral herds and flocks include grazing cattle, donkeys and sheep and browsing camels and goats. Pastoralism also relies on the diverse livestock products including milk, hides, meat, and blood and draft power.

Degehabur (Somali Dhagaxbuur) is one of the Woreda in the Somali Region of Ethiopia. Part of the Degehabur Zone, Degehabur is bordered on the southeast by the Gunagado and Koraha Zone, on the southwest by the Fiq Zone, on the west by Degehamedo, on the north by the Jijiga Zone, and on the east by Aware; it is frequently considered part of the Haud. The administrative center of this Woreda is Degehabur (CSA, 2007 & Hailu Ejara Kene,2011).

This Woreda has a total population of 115,555, of whom 65,081 are men and 50,474 women. While 30,027 or 25.99% are urban inhabitants, a further 45,818 or 39.65% are pastoralists. 98.6% of the population (CSA, 2007).

This Woreda takes the lion share (53%) (Sandford and Habtu, 2000) where the land are rain- fed, therefore, climate-sensitive agricultural production system (Tadesse, 2000) is more practiced here. There may not be many solutions to control climate so far but adaptations and adaptability still remain in the hand of human-beings wherever they are existing. Today the global warming(see below) and climate change effects are seen most of the parts in the world throughout the year where Ethiopia may not be exceptional .

Source: G.Thomas farmer John Cook, 2012

Ethiopia's history is associated, more often than not, with major natural and man-made disasters that have been affecting the population from time to time particularly livelihood of pastoralist and agro-pastoralists community. Recurrent drought, famine and recently floods have not only displaced these people but also made uncertainty about future in agricultural activities is serious concerned today. The problem is more prevalent in the north and south eastern lowlands of the country. The ecology in the area is fragile with an increasing trend of natural resources degradation while the pattern and distribution of rainfall are unpredictable and changed in nature. Agro-pastoral communities who reside in the arid and semi-arid environments are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change and variability specifically to the recurrent drought, floods that lead to often ethnical conflicts.

Despite these facts, the agro-pastoral communities have rich experiences which enable them to how to survive on such environmental pressures (Bamlaku *et al.*, 2015). Today in modernization and post modernization era when science and technology play a pivotal role for human development but in the measuring of natural disabilities and climatic vagaries are found to be unsatisfactory that still needs many researches and inventions. Village people particularly pastorals and agro-pastorals in many parts of Ethiopia in general and **Degehabur in particular** still have their own beliefs and practices on climate predictions while performing agricultural and related activities. Their belief and practice are so strong that they carry out agricultural activities in sustainable way through- out the sessions. Hence they develop indigenous climate risk prediction methods (see Table 1) that may not get place in the scientific jargons today but ultimately success comes to an extent while practicing agriculture and related activities for their sustainability.

Review of irrelevant literature

Many studies are found on climate change and its impact on sustainable- agriculture practices among farmers, pastoralists and agro-pastoralists community in Ethiopia but few have been focused about the value of the traditional rehearses on Climate predictions and its impact on sustainable- agriculture practices among - Pastoral-agro-pastoral communities that made a research gap for this study. There have been studies in the past like **Swift, (1988) defines agro-pastoralists as households** which obtain more than 25 percent but less than 50 percent of their gross incomes from livestock on communal grazing land and more than 50 percent from cropping activities. **Boef et al., (1993)** is generally defined as the “Knowledge of people of a particular area based on their interactions and experiences within the area, tradition, and their incorporation of knowledge emanating from elsewhere into their production and economic systems” According to **Dixon et al., (2001)** adverse climate change impacts are considered to be particularly strong in countries located in tropical Africa that depend on agriculture as their main source of livelihood. According to **EARO (2002)** the dry lands of Ethiopia are dominated by rangeland based livestock production systems known as pastoralism and agro-pastoralism (partly involved in opportunistic cropping) and represent a significant sector of the national agriculture in the country. **John,(2004)** define pastoralists as people who depend on livestock or the sale of livestock products for most of their income and consumption. **Mokhtari,(2005)** impact of drought on agriculture depends on the state of crops, the duration and amount of water storage. These phenomena are negatively affecting livelihoods of the developing world, and particularly marginalized groups in the poorest regions **IPCC (**

2007) refers to climate change as any change in climate over time, whether due to natural variability or as a result of human activity. Many African countries are vulnerable to climate change because their economies largely depend on climate-sensitive agricultural production system **Njoya (2009), IPCC(2007),** indicate that global warming and increased climate variability would be more intense in Africa than in the rest of the world and would severely affect African agriculture and pastoralism . **Maddison, (2007)** much of the available literature suggests that the overall impacts of climate change on agriculture especially in the tropics have been highly negative. Drought is ranked as the natural hazard with the greatest negative impact on human livelihood. According to **Carvajal (2007),** in the Human Development Report, the 2000-2006 periods showed that percentage of droughts have had an increasing tendency in Africa and Asia as well as in Europe. **Bamlaku et al., (2015)** expressed that despite these facts, the agro-pastoral communities have rich experiences of that enable them how to survive on such environmental pressures . **Nyong et al. (2007)** understanding, predicting and anticipating changes in weather and other climatic variables is very important for rural communities, whose livelihoods rely directly on weather and climate conditions. Local communities in the world observe climatic changes taking place in their environment which affect their livelihood choices. **Acharya(2011)** indigenous societies observe bio-physical animate and inanimate entities to make predictions about future and current weather variables that cannot be directly observed by the human senses. However, in many indigenous pastoral communities in Africa, factors such as land and natural resource dispossession. **Balehegn (2015),** state policies that favour centralization at the expense of bio-

regionalism. **Fratkin and Roth (2006); McGinnis (2005) ;Gilberthorpe and Hilson (2014)** have resulted in generational degradation and decline in the use of indigenous weather forecasting and other traditional knowledge. Similarly, climate change and associated increase in weather variability, especially in the arid and semi-arid ecosystems **Sivakumar et al., (2005)**, have resulted in decrease in the reliability of many of the traditional weather forecasting knowledge systems; as a result of this, many indigenous people are abandoning the use and generational transmission of such knowledge .**Balehegn (2016)** similarly, the Afar traditional pastoral production system in the Horn of Africa has been continuously under threat from climate change (as manifested by increased recurrent drought and extreme variability) and non-friendly pastoral state policies..**Peacock with Ragsdale's (1997)** formulation, the characteristics of community can be opposed to the characteristics of social relationships that are required for innovative action. **Comfort(1999)** has highlighted the importance of a sense of shared risk in order. **James M. Kendra and TriciaWachtendorf** for communities are to be able to organize to minimize the risk. Yet, if the risks are differentially distributed across the terrain of the community, then mobilizing attention and resources is likely to be more difficult. Moreover, differential distribution may result in disparities in risk perception which in turn may weaken community will or present barriers to decisive action.

Significant responsibility for the growth of climate denial is attributable to conservative think tanks. **Drivers of Climate Denial industry)**, they act as a means of influencing public opinion and policy makers. They began to take form in the 1970s but increased in activity in the early 1990s **Jacques et al. (2008)**. Their primary tactic

is to cast doubt on environmental science, alleging that the science is corrupt and either fabricated or exaggerated.

Therefore, this study is an attempt to relocate the understanding on Traditional rehearses on Climate predictions and its values in sustainable- agriculture practices among pastoral and agro-pastoral communities in Degehabur Woreda, Somali Regional State, Ethiopia: (A Study)

Theoretical Understanding

Theoretical understanding is to understand and development of theories. According to the United States National Academy of Sciences, Some scientific explanations are so well established that no new evidence is likely to alter them. Functional theory always asks the question of how a particular phenomenon operates to meet the survival needs or requisites of a larger social system, as the latter seeks to adapt to its environment. **Herbert Spencer (1874-1896)** emphasized the axes along which social systems differentiate, whereas **Emile Durkheim (1893)** examined the new bases for integration of social systems undergoing differentiation. Scholars like **Jurgen Habermas (1962,1970,1979,1984)**, the direct descendant of the Frankfurt School, continue to agonize over the loss of "the public sphere" (assuming that it actually had existed) and the invasion of the "life world" by a rationalized-bureaucratized economy and by a politico-administrative apparatus. Such critiques tend to be more philosophical than sociological, but they have inspired many to make similar claims about the power of the forces unleashed by capitalism to invade local cultures and personal self. **Allan & Turner(2001)** for **postmodernists**, the development of communication and transportation technologies, the expansions of capitalism to a global scale, and the capacity of high volume and far-reaching markets to commodity just about anything, including symbols

and lifestyles, are destroying local cultures, symbols of groups, and the integrity of the individual. **Darwinian evolutionary** theory seeing competition among actors over resources as one of the driving forces behind specialization of activities. Empirical research on the sciences suggests a manifest cultural, structural, and organizational disunity (**Galison, 1997**). **Aristotle (384–322 BC)** believed that knowledge was gained by empirical observation and experience. Our attempt to justify our beliefs logically by giving reasons results in the “regress of reasons.” **Galileo** made more discoveries that changed the world than anyone has ever made before or since. He saw what he believed to be mountains on the Moon, to have proved that the Milky Way was made up of stars, and to have seen four small bodies orbiting Jupiter. **Francis Bacon (1561–1626)** established inductive methodologies for scientific work. His pre-planned approach to the study of natural science forms the basis for the scientific method used today. To take the place of the established tradition that was in existence during his early life (which has been described as a combination of Scholasticism, humanism, and magic), he proposed an entirely new system based on empirical and inductive principles and the active development of new arts and inventions, a system whose ultimate goal would be the production of practical knowledge for “**the use and benefit of men**”

Discussions

Ethiopia is extremely vulnerable to drought and other natural disasters such as floods, heavy rains, frost and heat waves NMA (2007). Large parts of Ethiopia are dry, sub-humid, semi-arid and arid. The main climate hazards in Ethiopia are associated with droughts and floods. The most prominent trend has been a tendency towards lower rainfall during the main growing seasons (March–May and December–February). A decline of 15% has been

associated with anthropogenic Indian Ocean warming Brown and Funk (2008). While floods have historically never been a major economic hazard in Ethiopia, in recent years there have been significant socio-economic disruption due to flooding, e.g. 1997 and 2006 (Tarhule 2005, Conway *et al.* 2009).The Somali region has an arid (dry) and semi-arid climate. The region is hot in most of the year, with mean temperatures ranging from a low of (18 to 45 °C). Temperatures are cooler in the high altitudes especially in Jigjiga zone and parts of Afdher zone (e.g. Elkare); and are hotter in areas around the main rivers of the region including Wayb, Genale, Shabele and Dawa rivers BoFED, (2010). Annual rainfall ranges from 150mm in the low lying areas of the region to 660mm received in high altitude areas LCRDB(2009).

Grum (2010) in his studies show that the actual length of the rainy season is getting shorter and shorter through time. Similar trends of declining length of rainy seasons are being reported in many other low land areas Adugna and Aster,(2007) . These rapid changes of rain falls naturally indicate about climate change in these areas. The frequency of drought is viewed as increasing particularly over the past two decades. Except in more dry years, changes in the seasonality, distribution and regularity of rainfall were more of a concern than the overall amount of rainfall. The main rainy season is also seen as becoming progressively shorter it now starts later and finishes earlier than it used to be and the rains in general are becoming more unpredictable.

Tenacious and Protracted Droughts

Of all the environmental and socio-economic shocks and stressors people are facing, drought is the most common in pastoral and agro-pastoral areas. The eastern lowlands of Ethiopia are

vulnerable to drought and there have been notable droughts in this part of the country throughout human history Webb and Braun,(1994).

Livestock production is directly affected by drought through decreased pasture availability, leading to pasture shortage, overgrazing, and land degradation; decreased water availability, leading to water shortages and migration; decreased livestock disease resistance; decreased livestock productivity, in terms of milk and meat; emaciation and death of livestock and decreased livestock prices.

It is inevitable that climate change caused challenges to livelihood of major Africans, who depend on natural resources for their livelihood activities. Pastoral, agro-pastoral, and farming livelihoods are climate-sensitive as climate is one of the major inputs for the production and productivity of livestock and crops. Climate will seriously aggravate the impacts of current challenges in the drylands. Of all the natural resource-based land uses in the dry lands, pastoralism functions better within the context of wide rainfall variability and unpredictability.

Traditional knowledge rehearses

In response to absence of scientific information forecasting, the community has developed early warning system which bases traditional knowledge to forecast potential hazards and counteract their impacts. **Traditional knowledge** is generally defined as the “**Knowledge of people** of a particular area based on their interactions and experiences within the area, tradition, and their incorporation of knowledge emanating from elsewhere into their production and economic systems” Boef *et al.*, (1993). The Elders has been using this Indigenous knowledge overtime and handed down from generation to generation orally. The knowledge is evolved by locally defined conditions and needs.

Since historic past, local communities in different parts of the world have continued to rely on Indigenous Knowledge (IK) to conserve the environment and deal with natural disasters. Communities, particularly those who are vulnerable to droughts and floods prone areas have generated a vast body of IK on disaster prevention and mitigation through early warning and preparedness Anandaraja *et al.*, (2008; Svotwa *et al.*, 2007)(see table 1).The global scientific community has acknowledged the importance of IK. In addition, it was endorsed and recommended at the World Conference on Science held in Budapest, Hungary in 1999, that IK have must been integrated into science, particularly in the fields of environment and development (Warren, 1999).

Table 1: Indigenous Climate Risk Prediction Methods

Indicator	Signs	Time of Event	Prediction/Forecast
Star	In general there is no Hiding of	Before main rainy	Early and Enough
“sugra”	“Sugra” star throughout the year. Hide for 6 days in the East.	Season (February 15)	Rainfall in the coming Season.
	Hide for 60 days and came again.	Before main rainy Season (February)	Indicate lack of Rainfall with extreme Drought.
Star “Jimco	Based on Islamic Calendar “Hijri”,	Before main rainy	No Drought
Barkhadle”	if the Night that this star comes is 16 th Night of the month and that Night is Friday.	Season.	

	Sometimes it comes on the 22 nd Night of the month and that night is Friday.	Before main rainy Season.	Seven month of Drought from that event.
Seven Stars	☆☆☆ ☆ ☆		
	☆☆		
“Todobada Torbi”	This is the pattern of stars, they come from North-east and Go to North-west.		Early Normal and above Normal Rainfall is Expected from “Dira” season (MAM) and No rainfall in “Karan” (JASO) season.
	If the rectangular four stars are white and the remaining is hidden.	Throughout the Year	Normal Rainfall is Expected from “Karan” season (JASO) and No rainfall is Expected from “Dira” Season (MAM)
	If the sequenced three stars is white and the rectangular stars are Hidden.	Throughout the Year	Normal Rainfall is Expected from “Karan” season (JASO) and No rainfall is Expected from “Dira” Season (MAM)
Cold air	Very cold air “Tikimt” month, especially on Wednesday and Thursday from two nearby bonds, namely “Fardhaxanle” and “oondhere”	“Tikimt” Month	Loss and Damage of all crops.

Quake “ <i>Jibin</i> ”	Tremble sound from the south at Night.	At the End of Dry Season (January)	Extreme Rainfall
Wind	Wind comes from south (<i>Dabayl-foore</i>).	At the End of dry Season.	Start of Rainfall, but stops Early.
	Wind comes from East “ <i>Dabayl yuub</i> ”.	At the End of Dry Season.	Prolonged rain that covers many areas.
	Wind Comes from North-west “ <i>dabayl-jilaal</i> ”.	At the End of Dry Season.	Good rainfall in “ <i>Karan</i> ” Season (JASO).
Moon and assembled stars	Meets at the 16 th day of “ <i>Hijri</i> ” calendar	Close to the rainy season	Expectation of enough rainfall
	Go apart at the 16 th day of “ <i>Hijri</i> ” calendar	Close to the rainy season	Sign for No rainfall
Moon and star called “<i>Dirir</i>”	Moon and star “ <i>Dirir</i> ” became close to each other.	End of dry season	Good and abundant rainfall
	Star became far away from the moon	End of the dry season	Little or No rainfall

Source: Primary data

In order to achieve the full potential of participatory approaches to sustainable development, it is important that there should be greater recognition for the immense value of IK for development activities.

Sustainable agriculture practices

Sustainable agricultural practices play pivotal role in determining of socio-economic and political development for pastoralists and agro-pastoralists community. Today it is possible only when the potentiality of natural resources will be recognized through proper utilization when climate is not more favourable to sustainable agricultural activities most of the countries in Africa in general and Ethiopia in particular.

Ethiopia has tremendous untapped resource potentials for national development, and it is important to describe these potentials for policy and development makers to assist them devise appropriate strategies to exploit the resources. The resource base includes livestock, crop with diversified biodiversity, water, fertile soils, wildlife and tourism, energy resources and high values for anthropology and archeological resources.

It is also important to delineate resource potentials and economic values of pastoral areas for national development. The pastoral areas have diversified livestock species with high export potential. The country is often stated as the high potential livestock country in Africa and in the world, which gives opportunities for economic and social development going beyond the objectives of food security Kidane, (2015).

Proactive approaches to managing climate vulnerability among pastoral and agro-pastoral communities definitely a crucial step toward achieving sustainable agricultural practices thereby economic development of that region.

Conclusion and recommendations

Today sustainability of agriculture practices throughout African continents in general and Ethiopia in particular become a challenging task particularly pastoralists and agro-pastoralists community not only for climatic quirks but also for on time scientific supports to follow the change of climate and its impact. Therefore, indigenous knowledge and traditional beliefs and practices ultimately become a supportive weapon for agricultural activities where sustainability remains an issue and challenge. Farmer's motivation and intrinsic values play again a fundamental role in adopting various climates thereby sustainable agriculture practices in Degehabur Woreda, Somali Regional State. Decision making process also play major role to accept and apply indigenous methods and tools in appropriate time of production cycles become also a real issue and challenge before these communities when sustainability is concerned. The following recommendations are made for formulating policies and programs in this regard.

Recommendations

Pastoralists and agro-pastoralists in the study area are solely dependent on rain for pasture production and rain fed agriculture. Because of this they are highly susceptible to the erratic and shortage of rainfall. So improving their capacity to adapt to climate change is crucial. The following recommendations are put forward.

- **To get information of future weather events** and take right measures accordingly the pastoralists and agro-pastoralists needs a well-built and designed early warning system. Therefore, concerned bodies should have to support the particularly the farmers; through proper weather forecast. Thus, it is important to

toughen the meteorological station in Jigjiga district so as to provide reliable and timely weather information on a daily basis.

- **Improved seed, early maturing crop variety and drought resistant** breed of livestock is needed to bring up and capacitate the pastoral and agro-pastoral in the study area; Therefore, governmental and Non-governmental organization working in the study area recommended to work on these issues.
- **To enable valuable early warning information** that enable them to destock or restock their livestock well time in advance before extreme climatic events emerges over the region, the concerned are ought to use radio/TV for the transmission of such information.
- **To explore more valuable indigenous knowledge** of climate risk forecasts, giving recognition and documenting this knowledge is needed and also the concerned bodies are ought to use both scientific and indigenous forecasting systems in conjunction with one another, so as to increases the willingness of the local community in using the scientific one.

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